

The Construction of the Set of Stable States for Constrained Systems with Open-Loop Unstable Plants

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Abstract

Control in the presence of hard control and state constraints, and open-loop unstable plants, is addressed. A methodology for the construction of a set of stable states of a tracking control system is presented. A saturation avoidance control strategy is employed, and the exogenous reference signal is modified nonlinearly so that the controlled process state is constrained to a positively invariant set. Stability is guaranteed for all initial states in this set. The said set is an arbitrarily close approximation of the maximal statically admissible set. Characterization of this set is an important stepping stone in the synthesis of tracking controllers.

1 Introduction

The problem of high amplitude tracking control of dynamic reference signals in the face of hard control and state constraints, and open-loop unstable plants is investigated. In the case of open-loop unstable plants and control and state constraints, global stability cannot be achieved. Then, one is interested in characterizing the largest possible positively invariant set of initial states, and in restricting the state vector to this set. Here, the maximal statically admissible set is characterized for a discrete-time constrained control system, and a nonlinear control methodology is proposed that restricts the state vector to this positively invariant set. Moreover, the proposed method does not unnecessarily restrict the feasible reference signal to statically admissible values.

The saturation mitigation strategy employed entails saturation avoidance to guarantee closed-loop system BIBO stability. This naturally leads to controller design methodologies which are based on the concepts of static admissibility and positively invariant sets, see e.g. [1], [2], [4], [5], and [6]. In these investigations the exogenous reference signal, r , is modified by a nonlinear element, N , which outputs a feasible reference signal,

r' , so that the controlled process state is constrained to a positively invariant (admissible) set - see e.g., Fig. 1. The control architecture shown in Fig. 1 is designed to afford slewing control while at the same time preserving small signal performance. In other words, in the small signal regime, the nonlinearity, N , is transparent and linear action is preserved. A common characteristic of these methods, when applied to the tracking control problem, is that to obtain a BIBO stable closed-loop system, the feasible reference signal, r' , is restricted to statically admissible values for all time. However, as shown in [3], this sacrifices achievable tracking performance since there are certainly cases where a reference signal that is not statically admissible over a finite time interval would not necessarily result in saturation.

In this paper, the dynamic nonlinearity in [2] is replaced by a static nonlinear element. Furthermore, this paper departs from previous work in that it investigates a controller synthesis methodology which does not require static admissibility of the feasible reference signal to obtain a BIBO stable closed-loop system. Lyapunov instability is not incurred. Moreover, when r is statically admissible asymptotic tracking is achieved. An efficient algorithm for the construction of this set is given.

The paper is organized as follows. Sect. 2 presents a method to remove the requirement of static admissibility of the feasible reference signal. This concept is illustrated with a second-order example in Sect. 3, and conclusions and remarks are presented in Sect. 4.

2 Projection of Polyhedral Sets onto a Subspace

The discrete-time LTI controlled process of Fig. 1 includes the bare plant and linear feedback control law. The controlled process constraints may be expressed in terms of an output constraint vector, y_c , with appropriate choices of matrices C_{cl} and D_{cl} , and constraint set,

$Y \subset \mathbb{R}^p$. Then, the controlled process and constraints are given by

$$\begin{aligned} x(t+1) &= A_{cl}x(t) + B_{cl}r'(t) \\ y_c(t) &= C_{cl}x(t) + D_{cl}r'(t) \in Y \subset \mathbb{R}^p \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The output constraint vector, y_c , may represent actuator displacement and rate constraints, or constraints on other system parameters.

The following nonrestrictive assumptions are made: *i*) A_{cl} is asymptotically stable, *ii*) The pair (A_{cl}, C_{cl}) is observable, *iii*) Y is polyhedral, and contains the origin; viz., Y is expressed as

$$Y = \{y_c \in \mathbb{R}^p : f_i(y_c) \leq 0, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, s\} \quad (2)$$

where the s functionals, $f_i : \mathbb{R}^p \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, are linear or affine in y_c , with $f_i(0) \leq 0$.

In [2] the nonlinear element of Fig. 1 is a first-order, low-pass filter whose state vector is the modified reference signal, r' . The controlled process is augmented with the low-pass filter, which results in a Lyapunov stable augmented system with augmented state vector $x_g \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$. Now, the maximal output admissible set, O_∞ , is the set of all initial states, $x_g \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$, such that the unforced augmented system response does not violate the output constraints for all time.

Since the augmented system is only Lyapunov stable, the maximal output admissible set can not be characterized by a finite number of inequalities. However, in [2] a finitely determined ε approximation, O_∞^ε , is developed by restricting r' to the interior of the set of statically admissible constant reference signals. In our case O_∞^ε may be expressed as

$$O_\infty^\varepsilon = \{x_g \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1} : \Gamma_g x_g \leq \beta_g\} \subset \mathbb{R}^{n+1} \quad (3)$$

Exploiting the inequalities (3) in the constraint avoidance strategy necessarily results in limiting both the controlled system state vector and the modified reference signal, r' , to statically admissible values. A method to remove the restriction of static admissibility from r' is presented next.

The following definitions will be useful in our discussion.

Definition 1 *The set of statically admissible inputs, R_s , for the controlled process defined by eq. (1), is the set of constant inputs for which the associated equilibrium point is admissible. That is,*

$$R_s = \{r' \in \mathbb{R} : H_o r' \in Y\} \quad (4)$$

where the matrix $H_o = C_{cl}(I - A_{cl})^{-1}B_{cl} + D_{cl}$.

Definition 2 *The set of statically admissible states, X_s , for the controlled process defined by eq. (1), is the set of initial states for which there exists a statically admissible reference signal such that the ensuing trajectory does not violate the system's state and control constraints for all time. That is,*

$$X_s = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : \exists r' \in R_s \quad \text{s.t.} \quad y_c(t) \in Y \quad \forall t \in I^+\} \quad (5)$$

X_s is the projection of O_∞ onto the plane $r' = 0$. Moreover, an approximation of X_s , $X_s^\varepsilon \subset X_s$, can be characterized with a finite set of linear inequalities by projecting the polyhedron, $O_\infty^\varepsilon \subset O_\infty$, onto the subspace \mathbb{R}^n , viz.,

$$X_s^\varepsilon = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : \Gamma_\varepsilon x \leq \beta_\varepsilon\} \subset X_s \quad (6)$$

An algorithm which generates the desired linear inequalities of eq. (6), given the linear inequalities of eq. (3) is presented next.

First, note that since $O_\infty^\varepsilon \subset \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$ is bounded, convex and polyhedral, X_s^ε is also bounded, convex, and polyhedral. Also, the origin is an interior point of O_∞^ε , and thus an interior point of X_s^ε . Finally, note that the set of hyperplanes,

$$\gamma_i^T v_i = b_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, N, \quad v_i \in h_i$$

supports X_s^ε . Here, γ_i^T and b_i are the i^{th} rows of Γ_ε and β_ε respectively, and v_i is one of n vertices contained in the i^{th} hyperplane, denoted by h_i .

The single input case, $r \in \mathbb{R}^1$ is now considered. Assume

$\Gamma_g = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_{g1}^T \\ \vdots \\ \gamma_{gm}^T \end{bmatrix}$ is an $M \times (n+1)$ matrix, and let $\gamma_{gi}^T = [\gamma_{gi1} \quad \tilde{\gamma}_{gi}^T]$. Then, the vertices of the polytope, X_s^ε , may be obtained by solving the LPs

$$\max_{x_g} (c_i^T x_g) \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \Gamma_g x_g \leq \beta_g, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, M \quad (7)$$

where

$$c_i^T = [0 \quad \tilde{\gamma}_{gi}^T];$$

cases where $c_i^T = 0$ are ignored. Each c_i^T produces an extremal vector, $x_{gi}^* = \begin{bmatrix} r_i^* \\ x_i^* \end{bmatrix}$. Moreover, x_i^* is the projection of $x_{gi}^* \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$ onto the \mathbb{R}^n subspace. The LP (7) generally generates $K < M$ unique vertices.

Important properties of the set of unique vertices, $V = \{x_1^*, \dots, x_K^*\} = \{v_1, \dots, v_K\}$, obtained from the solution of the LP (7) include the following:

(p1): $v_j \in C_0(X_s^\varepsilon) \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, K$, (p2): Each of the hyperplanes that support X_s^ε contains at least n

vertices from V , (p3): Each $v_i \in V$ is contained in at least n of the hyperplanes that support X_s^ε .

In addition to the above properties it generally transpires that the vertices of X_s^ε are grouped in several clusters in the state space. This suggests that a set $X_s^\delta \subset X_s^\varepsilon$ may be generated from a set, $V' \subset V$, with minimal loss of volume. For example, V' may be obtained from V by requiring that all elements of V' be a specified Euclidean distance from each other. The set X_s^δ is given by

$$X_s^\delta = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : \Gamma_\delta x \leq \beta_\delta\} \subset X_s^\varepsilon \quad (8)$$

The end result is to eliminate closely spaced corners from X_s^ε , and to reduce the number of inequality constraints required to characterize X_s^δ . Unfortunately, X_s^δ is not necessarily positively invariant, but this is easily overcome by taking advantage of the fact that $X_s^\delta \subset X_s^\varepsilon$.

2.1 Generating the Hyperplanes

Let h_i denote the i^{th} hyperplane that supports X_s^ε . Since the origin is in the interior of X_s^ε , h_i is uniquely defined by the triple, (γ_i^T, v_i, b_i) , where γ_i^T is a linear functional, and the i^{th} row of Γ , $v_i \in V$ is one of the n vertices contained in h_i , and b_i is an arbitrary, non-zero, scalar. We require that b_i be chosen such that $\gamma_i^T(0) < b_i$. Thus, $b_i > 0 \forall i = 1, \dots, N$. Also, note that

$$\gamma_i^T v \leq b_i \quad \forall v \in V \quad (9)$$

This is due to the convexity of X_s^ε .

Now, if the n vertices, v_{i_1}, \dots, v_{i_n} , contained in the i^{th} hyperplane are known, and we choose $b_i = 1$, then $\gamma_i^T \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is given by

$$\gamma_i^T = [1 \quad \dots \quad 1] [v_{i_1} \quad \dots \quad v_{i_n}]^{-1} \quad (10)$$

The problem then, is to determine the number of hyperplanes, N , that make up $C_0(X_s^\varepsilon)$, and which n vertices are contained in each hyperplane. The following algorithm accomplishes this task.

First, an initial set of $n+1$ hyperplanes are constructed from an initial set of $n+1$ vertices, $V_{n+1} \subset V$, using eq. (10), and the $n+1$ unique combinations of n out of $n+1$ vertices in V_{n+1} . Moreover, the initial $n+1$ vertices are selected so that the resultant polytope, $X_{n+1}^\varepsilon \subset X_s^\varepsilon$ contains the origin. This is verified by insuring that each of the initial $n+1$ inequalities, $\gamma_i^T x \leq 1$, $i = 1, \dots, n+1$, is satisfied for each of the initial $n+1$ vertices.

Now, we have the initial polytope,

$$X_{n+1}^\varepsilon = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : \Gamma_{n+1} x \leq \beta_{n+1}\} \subset X_s^\varepsilon$$

Where $\Gamma_{n+1} \in \mathbb{R}^{(n+1) \times n}$ and $\beta_{n+1} \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$. Next, additional vertices from V are incorporated one at a time until all vertices are included. This is accomplished by first determining which of the existing inequalities are not satisfied for each new vertex. Then the vertices associated with the failed inequalities are used together with the new vertex to generate new hyperplanes and inequalities.

Determining which inequalities are not satisfied for a new vertex is accomplished as follows. Assume k vertices from V have been incorporated to obtain

$$\Gamma_k = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_{k_1}^T \\ \vdots \\ \gamma_{k_p}^T \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times n}, \quad \beta_k \in \mathbb{R}^p,$$

and the polytope

$$X_k^\varepsilon = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : \Gamma_k x \leq \beta_k\} \subset X_s^\varepsilon$$

Also, let v_{k+1} denote the new vertex. On the first pass, $k = p = n + 1$. Also, recall that all elements of β_k are 1. Now, compute

$$\zeta_k = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\|\gamma_{k_1}\|_2} \gamma_{k_1}^T v_{k+1} \\ \vdots \\ \frac{1}{\|\gamma_{k_p}\|_2} \gamma_{k_p}^T v_{k+1} \end{bmatrix},$$

and note that if

$$\zeta_{k_i} - \frac{1}{\|\gamma_{k_i}\|_2} > 0, \quad (11)$$

then the linear inequality, $\gamma_{k_i}^T x \leq 1$, is not satisfied, and is therefore invalid.

In general, for $n \geq 3$, adding a new vertex may invalidate several existing inequalities. Moreover, it may not be immediately clear how many new hyperplanes should be created, and which vertices feature together in each new hyperplane.

This issue can be resolved by noting the following. Failed hyperplanes are contiguous. This is due to the convexity of X_k^ε . Also, the intersection of two supporting hyperplanes contains $n-1$ vertices and is an "edge" of X_k^ε . Not only does an edge contain $n-1$ vertices, but is also contained in exactly two supporting hyperplanes, and has co-dimension two, whereas hyperplanes have co-dimension one. Finally, edges contained in failed hyperplanes may be categorized as either "failed" edges or "valid" edges. Failed edges are those edges that are contained in the intersection of two failed hyperplanes. Valid edges are those edges that are contained in only one failed hyperplane.

Now it transpires that failed edges do not feature in $C_0(X_{k+1}^\varepsilon)$, while valid edges are each contained in exactly one new hyperplane. Also, each new hyperplane

contains exactly one valid edge. This situation follows from the convexity of X_k^ε , the fact that each vertex is contained in $C_0(X_{k+1}^\varepsilon)$, and the fact that valid edges are contained in existing hyperplanes that were not invalidated by v_{k+1} . Thus, the number of new hyperplanes is equal to the number of valid edges, and the $n - 1$ vertices from each valid edge are combined with v_{k+1} to obtain a new hyperplane, using eq. (10).

In summary, as each new vertex is incorporated, it is tested against all existing inequalities using eq. (11). Next, failed and valid edges are identified from the set of failed hyperplanes. The $n - 1$ vertices from each valid edge are combined with the new vertex, v_{k+1} , to form new hyperplanes, and ultimately new linear inequalities. Finally, it is important to note that this algorithm is performed off-line, and only the resultant inequalities of eq. (6) are used in the on-line constraint mitigation algorithm.

3 Second-Order Example

The following second-order example provides an illuminating demonstration of the methods described in this paper. Consider the second-order system

$$\dot{x}(t) = Ax(t) + Bu(t) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 2 & 1 \end{bmatrix} x(t) + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 2 \end{bmatrix} u(t) \quad (12)$$

where the constrained control signal, $u(t)$, is given by

$$-1 \leq u(t) = k_x x(t) + k_r r'(t) \leq 1 \quad (13)$$

and, the inner-loop control system's gains

$$k_x = \begin{bmatrix} -9 & -2.5 \end{bmatrix}, \text{ and } k_r = 8 \quad (14)$$

have been chosen to provide good small signal tracking performance. Notice that the open-loop system dynamics matrix is unstable, with eigenvalues at -1 and 2 . Furthermore, statically admissible values of r' satisfy

$$-1 \leq r' \leq 1$$

Let $X_s(r_o)$ denote the set of statically admissible states for a constant $r = r_o$. As a benchmark, the true statically admissible set, X_s , is manually constructed by obtaining $X_s(r_o)$ for constant, statically admissible reference signals that satisfy $-1 \leq r_o \leq 1$, and then generating

$$X_s = \bigcup_{-1 \leq r_o \leq 1} X_s(r_o)$$

Figure 2 shows $X_s(0)$ inscribed within X_s . In that Figure 2 is a rendition of the true X_s , it is the benchmark to which any approximation must be compared.

An equivalent discrete-time system is obtained using a sampling rate of 100 Hz , and is given by

$$\begin{aligned} x(t+1) &= \begin{bmatrix} 1.0001 & 1.0051 \times 10^{-2} \\ 2.0101 \times 10^{-2} & 1.0102 \end{bmatrix} x(t) \\ &\quad + \begin{bmatrix} 1.0034 \times 10^{-4} \\ 2.0101 \times 10^{-2} \end{bmatrix} u(t) \\ -1 &\leq u(t) = k_x x(t) + k_r r'(t) \leq 1 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Now, the set of inequalities, eq. (3), which characterize $O_\infty^\varepsilon \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ are obtained using the methods of [2]. In this case we have $\Gamma_g \in \mathbb{R}^{246 \times 3}$ and $\beta_g \in \mathbb{R}^{246}$.

The methods of Section 2 are used to obtain $X_s^\varepsilon \subset \mathbb{R}^2$. For this problem, the Linear Program of eq. (7) generates 86 unique vertices from the 246 rows of Γ_g . Thus, for this problem X_s^ε is characterized with 86 linear inequalities.

To illustrate the effects of thinning the set of vertices, X_s^δ is characterized using a 26 element subset of V . The subset was generated by requiring that all elements be a specified Euclidean distance, $d = 0.009$, from each other, Fig. 3. Comparing Figure 3 to Figure 2 shows that there is very little volume lost in X_s^δ . However, there are only 26 inequalities required to characterize X_s^δ here, versus the 246 inequalities required to characterize O_∞^ε . In fact, a reasonable approximation to X_s may be obtained for this problem with as little as 8 linear inequalities. In cases where the dimension of the controlled process state vector is greater than two, the trade-off between computational burden and volume of X_s^δ , for various subsets of V , may be estimated by computing the maximum and minimum steady-state responses allowed by the resultant linear inequalities of eq. (8).

3.1 Tracking Controller Synthesis

Assume $x(0) \in X_s^\varepsilon$, and define the sets

$$R_\varepsilon(t) = \{r : \Gamma_\varepsilon x(t+1) \leq \beta_\varepsilon\}$$

and

$$R_f(t) = \{r : y_c(t) \in Y\}$$

Then, a reasonable control strategy is to choose $r'(t)$ at each time increment so as to

$$\min_{r'(t)} |r(t) - r'(t)| \text{ s. t. } r'(t) \in R_\varepsilon(t) \cap R_f(t) \quad (16)$$

Then $x(t) \in X_s^\varepsilon$ for all $t \in I^+$, the controlled process constraints are not violated, and the closed-loop system of Fig. 1 will be BIBO stable. Feasibility is guaranteed, by construction. Moreover, r' is not restricted to statically admissible values. The set of constraints is determined off-line. Hence, on-line implementation is easy since the constraint imposed on $r'(t)$ by each

inequality of eq. (6) is given by a simple algebraic formula. More aggressive control strategies may also be implemented which provide faster response times.

If X_s^ϵ is replaced with X_s^δ , then $R_\epsilon(t)$ is replaced with $R_\delta(t)$ in the above control strategy, where $R_\delta(t)$ is defined in the obvious manner. However, X_s^δ is not positively invariant. Thus, when $x(t) \in \partial(X_s^\delta)$ it may transpire that $R_\delta(t) \cap R_f(t)$ is empty. In this case choosing $r'(t) = \min_{r \in R_f} |r|$ results in $y_c(t) \in Y$ and

$x(t+1) \in X_s^\epsilon \stackrel{set}{=} X_s^\delta$. Also, when $\beta_\delta - \Gamma_\delta x(t) < \epsilon$, where ϵ is a small positive number, replace the constraint in eq. (16) with $r'(t) \in R_\delta(t) \cap R_s^\delta \cap R_f(t)$. Where

$$R_s^\delta = \left\{ r : \Gamma_\delta (I - A_{cl})^{-1} B_{cl} r \leq \beta_\delta \right\}$$

This insures convergence to a state $x \in X_s^\delta$, and prevents numerical precision problems.

4 Conclusions

The concepts of static admissibility and positively invariant sets play central roles in the nonlinear controller synthesis methodology which addresses the problem of high amplitude dynamic reference signal tracking in the face of hard control and state constraints, and open-loop unstable plants. Current controller synthesis methodologies based on these concepts restrict the feasible reference signal to statically admissible values. In this paper we have developed a controller synthesis methodology which allows statically inadmissible feasible reference signals, and at the same time obtains the largest possible statically admissible set of states. Moreover, the system response is bounded irrespective of the exogenous reference signal.

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Figure 1: Dual loop tracking controller architecture

Figure 2: Convex hulls of X_s and $X_s(0)$

Figure 3: X_s^δ from a 26 element subset of V